

(Assessment of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Practical ... Eva. O. O. & Omoniwa, F. A. 2025)

Assessment of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Practical Skills Acquisition in Computer Science among Undergraduate Students in Usmanu Danfodio University Sokoto

EVA .O. ONYEKA¹

evawine@yahoo.com

08075381464

OMONIWA, Femi Adekunle (Ph.D.)²

femmy.omoniwa@gmail.com

femmy.omoniwa23@fcezaria.edu.ng

08069425183

¹Department of Computer Science, Federal University of Education, Zaria

²Department of Curriculum and Instruction, Federal University of Education, Zaria

Abstract

This paper assessed laboratory instructional strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS Affiliated Programme. Three (3) objectives and research questions each were formulated to guide the study. The study adopted descriptive survey design and population of the study comprised of all 300 level UDUS students of 2022/2023 academic session (of the formerly affiliated Federal College of Education, Zaria). Since the population (361) is not as large as in other researches, the researchers have decided to use same as sample size using purposive sampling technique. Questionnaire was the sole instrument used for data collection in this study from the respondents (students). Data analysis was undertaken using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and simple percentages. The study revealed that the use of laboratory instructional strategy by teachers has assisted UDUS B.Ed students in the practical skill acquisition of computer science in FUE, Zaria to a great extent. FUE, Zaria have the required facilities that supports the use of laboratory instructional strategy towards the practical skills acquisition in computer science for UDUS B.Ed students. The effects of the use of laboratory instructional strategy on the practical skills acquisition in computer science among UDUS B.Ed students in FUE, Zaria, is relatively positive and high. Thus, the study recommended the need for education managers to advocate for the strong use of this strategy in teaching science related subject. Finally, this strategy is student - centeredness and should therefore be encouraged in all teacher training institutions when teaching computer science students.

Keywords: Computer Science, Instructional Strategy, Practical Skills Acquisition

Introduction

(Assessment of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Practical ... Eva. O. O. & Omoniwa, F. A. 2025)

The use of computers today is key to the activities of individuals, groups and organizations at achieving a certain goals or the other. Thus, as important as it is, the practical knowledge of how to effectively use it is still in dilemma. This is because, there are those who could not afford it (aside their mobile phones), others have it for the mere sake of the time they would be asked if they have it or not. The other category are those who could not use it for so many things even as a student in the institution under study aside phone calls and/or short messages. Although, it is a known fact that computer science has become a useful “tool in different sectors of the economy. In fact, there is no discipline at the moment where knowledge of computer science is not being used for one operation or the other. Computers are being used in the airports to control flights.

It is equally being used in the hospitals to diagnose, treat and manage diseases. In the field of communication, networking and internet connectivity has turn the whole world into a global village. Marketing Robot is also being developed to take care of sales in big marketing organizations. In a nutshell, computer science has become so useful and popular to the extent that all countries are training and developing her citizens to be at least computer literate. Meanwhile, the Nigerian government via her educational system has introduced computer science otherwise referred to as information and communication technology (ICT) or data processing as a subject in all schools including primary, secondary and tertiary institutions. But despite all the efforts of government, the performance of students is abysmal as wide gap exist between their theoretical and practical knowledge (Omoniwa nd).

This was suspected to be as a result of the teaching method so adopted by those saddled to teach the subject (or course) at the different levels. Many teaching methods have so far been employed such as discussion, assignment, lecture, laboratory among others. The focus of this study however, is to assess laboratory instructional strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students of UDUS Affiliated Programme in the former Federal College of Education, Zaria. Laboratory method of teaching according to Akuto, Aduloju and Odeh (2012) in Chibabi, Umoru, Onah and Itodo (2018) is a process where the students are in direct contact with the concept or processes they are learning. This includes any activity involving students in real situations using genuine materials and properly working equipments.

(Assessment of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Practical ... Eva. O. O. & Omoniwa, F. A. 2025)

The authors added that the use of laboratory method of teaching aids the development of visual, perceptual and manipulative skills and also makes learning permanent (retention) among students. In using this method, the teacher does not take recourse to lecturing nor to demonstration of experiment. Rather, the students are encouraged to derive the laws and principles of science themselves by actually performing the experiments. The students are given all necessary materials and equipments in the laboratory along with their proper instructions for carrying out their experiments with their own initiative and effort. The observations are recorded and the results are inferred. It helps the students to understand complex abstract ideas and gives students an opportunity to participate in the process and have an appreciation for the methods of science.

It is further considered that the knowledge and skills gained through laboratory method is more lasting and permanent as they learn by their own experience, observation, testing and verification. In all these, the teacher is expected to guide the trainee teachers on what to do during the session and at achieving worthwhile results. For this reason, it is believed that constant practice leads to proficiency in what the learners learn during classroom instruction hence, the dictum “practice makes perfect”. This has given rise to the expectation that laboratory facilities should be adequately provided to schools for effective teaching and learning. Important areas of literature reviewed in this paper are sub - titled below as:

Use of Laboratory Strategy by Computer Science Teachers

Laboratory experiences provide opportunities for teachers to model best practices in the study of scientific concepts, including application of scientific methodologies, respect for life and the environment, inclusion of learners of all abilities, and consistent adherence to safety standards. Thus, study in a laboratory is an integral and essential part of science courses (Odubunni, and Balagun in Gonca, Aytakin, Burckin and Umut, 2016). This being the case, is with expectations that this method be used as much as possible to assist the students to understand the practical aspect of the course of study. Tobin (1990) quoted by Hamidu, Ibrahim and Mohammed, 2014 wrote that: “Laboratory activities appears as a way to learn with understanding and, at the same time, engage in a process of constructing knowledge by doing science”. He also suggested that meaningful and quality learning is possible in the laboratory if students are given opportunities to manipulate equipment and

(Assessment of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Practical ... Eva. O. O. & Omoniwa, F. A. 2025)

materials in order to be able to construct their knowledge of phenomena and related scientific concepts.

Availability of instructional Facilities for Laboratory Strategy

There is usually a strong move to emphasize the dependence of science (computer class) teaching on the existence of a well - equipped laboratory. With the laboratory experience, students will be able to translate what they have read in their texts to practical realities, thereby enhancing their understanding of the learnt concepts. Farombi (1998) in Yara (2010) argued the saying that seeing is believing is the effect of using laboratories in the teaching and learning of science and other science related disciplines as students tend to understand and recall what they see more than what they hear.

Effects of Laboratory Strategy on Practical Skills Acquisition in Computer Science

Science educators have believed that the laboratory is an important means of instruction in science since late in the 19th century. Laboratory instruction was considered essential because it provided training in observation, supplied detailed information, and aroused pupils' interest. These same reasons are still accepted almost 100 years later. In a laboratory, students work individually or in small groups on a question, problem or hypothesis. The distinction between laboratory and traditional classroom learning is that activities are student - centered, with students actively engaged in hands-on, minds - on activities using laboratory techniques. (Lazarowitz and Tamir, 1994 cited by Hamidu, Ibrahim and Mohammed, 2014).

Laboratory is very important and essential to the teaching of science and success of any science course is much dependent on the laboratory provision made for it. Lending credence to this statement, Yara (2010) in Hamidu, Ibrahim and Mohammed, 2014) said that there is a general consensus among science educators that laboratory occupies a central position in science instruction. It could be conceptualized as a place, where theoretical work is practicalized and practicals in any learning experiences involve students in activities such as observing, counting, measuring, experimenting, recording and carrying out fieldwork.

(Assessment of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Practical ... Eva. O. O. & Omoniwa, F. A. 2025)

Preference of Laboratory Strategy for Practical Skills Acquisition in Computer Science

There are a number of teaching methods available for teacher's use in teaching Computer Science. These methods are classified into two major groups namely traditional (teacher - centered) and contemporary methods (students - centered). The preference for this method of teaching (laboratory) is to enable students to be actively involved in knowledge acquisition and retention over a period of time. As in the case of traditional method, students are rarely exposed to practical work because science teachers do not place much value and attention on the process of science through laboratory activities since they feel it takes time away from teaching to cover the prescribed examination - driven curriculum (Abamba, 2012).

This has also encouraged teachers and students to depend on external examination instructional manuals instead of preparing students through student - centred methods. It is quite obvious from the aforementioned, that practical knowledge of the use of computers for multifaceted tasks in the different nation's industry will be a lot more achievable if laboratory method is adopted in schools. However, there are many issues with the use of laboratory method in teacher colleges for practical knowledge of computer science. In his contribution, Kofo (2012) pointed out that science teachers do not usually find it convenient to make laboratory method the center of their instruction. They usually complain of lack of materials and equipment to carry out practical work.

At the same time, it is possible that some of these materials and equipment may be locked up in the school laboratory store without teachers being aware of their existence. The conditions under which many teachers function do not engender any enthusiasm to use the laboratory method of teaching computer science even where they know that these materials and equipment are available. To cap it all, higher institutions in Nigeria charged with the responsibility of training computer science teachers at all levels, are increasingly turning out teachers without requisite laboratory experience. A common reason usually given is shortage of laboratory facilities. Such trained computer science teachers usually lack the necessary confidence to conduct practical classes with their students.

Objectives of the Study

The following specific objectives guided this study:

(Assessment of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Practical ... Eva. O. O. & Omoniwa, F. A. 2025)

1. Assess the extent of use of laboratory strategy for practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS.
2. Find out if the required instructional facilities are available in UDUS for the use of laboratory strategy for practical skills acquisition in computer science.
3. Examine the effects of laboratory strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS.

Research Questions

This study shall be guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent does the use of laboratory strategy assist undergraduate students in practical skills acquisition in computer science in UDUS?
2. Do UDUS have the required instructional facilities for the use of laboratory strategy for practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students?
3. What are the effects of laboratory strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS?

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive survey research design. Yin (2014) argues descriptive survey research design is useful for providing a comprehensive understanding of a phenomenon or population. Population for this study was comprised of all year III UDUS students of 2022/2023 academic session (of the formerly affiliated Federal College of Education, Zaria). Since the population is not as large as in other researches, the researchers have decided to use same as sample size. Therefore, a sample size of three hundred and sixty - one (361) students was selected at random for this study using purposive sampling technique. In any research as this, purposive sampling technique which is also judgment sampling is a non - probability sampling method where participants are selected based on the researchers' judgment and expertise. It allows for selection of sample that is representative of the population, but not necessarily randomly selected (Creswell, 2014).

The sole instrument used for data collection in this study was questionnaire and titled "questionnaire on assessment of laboratory strategy on practical skills

(Assessment of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Practical ... Eva. O. O. & Omoniwa, F. A. 2025)

acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students” (QALSPSACS). Pilot study was conducted in Kaduna State College of Education, Gidan Waya an affiliate institution to Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and a reliability co-efficient of 0.89 was obtained. Data analysis was undertaken using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and simple percentages on the reseach questions formulated for this study.

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: To what extent does the use of laboratory strategy assist undergraduate students in practical skills acquisition in computer science in UDUS? The respondents questionnaire was adopted alongside Likert four point rating scale of strongly agreed (SA), agreed (A), disagreed (D) and strongly disagreed (SD) respectively. There are five (5) item statements in the table below which the respondents had responded to.

Table 1: Respondents’ opinion on the use of laboratory strategy as it assist in practical skill acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students

S/N	Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	STD
1.	Laboratory method helps a lot in the acquisition of knowledge of computers, its use and functions.	162	80	90	29	3.038	1.010
2.	Laboratory method helps in the retention of knowledge	168	68	77	48	2.986	1.101
3.	It is a less suitable method in the teaching of practical oriented subject like computer.	129	110	70	52	2.875	1.055
4.	It is a suitable method of teaching which has attracted students’ interest in the subject.	196	115	33	17	3.357	0.834
5.	The use of laboratory method will further assist the students to earn a living for themselves to support their studies.	161	130	30	40	3.141	0.977
Cumulative Mean						3.079	

Source: Field work (2024)

Decision/threshold mean =2.500

The extent to which the use of laboratory method by teachers assisted UDUS B.Ed students in the practical acquisition of knowledge in computer science in FUE, Zaria is quite high. This is as the cumulative mean response of 3.079 is higher than the 2.500 decision/threshold mean. Specifically, most of the students asserted that the method in question is suitable for teaching and has attracted students’ interest in the subject. This view attracted the highest mean agreement level of 3.357 as details showed that a combined total of 315 were in agreement and 50 others disagreed.

(Assessment of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Practical ... Eva. O. O. & Omoniwa, F. A. 2025)

Also, most respondents believed that the use of laboratory method will further assist the students to earn a living for themselves in order to support their studies. As this view attracted the second highest mean of 3.141 as details showed that while a combined total of 290 were in agreement the rest 70 were in disagreement.

Research Question Two: Do UDUS have the required instructional facilities for the use of laboratory strategy for practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students? The respondents questionnaire was adopted alongside Likert four point rating scale of strongly agreed (SA), agreed (A), disagreed (D) and strongly disagreed (SD) respectively. There are five (5) item statements in table 2 below which the respondents had responded to.

Table 2: Respondents’ opinion on instructional facilities for the use of laboratory strategy in practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students

S/N	Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	STD
1.	Electricity supply to the University is constantly available whenever this method is to be used.	108	96	104	53	2.717	1.047
2.	There is inadequate computers and other accessories for use whenever this method is to be used.	164	74	80	35	3.022	1.033
3.	Adequate manpower with requisite knowledge of computers and method to use can be found in FUE, Zaria	177	128	36	20	3.279	0.857
4.	Learning environment where laboratory method can be use to teach and acquire knowledge in computers are unavailable in FUE, Zaria.	141	112	64	44	2.969	1.028
5.	Laboratory method is mostly used by experienced lecturers at the expense of their inexperience counterparts.	165	132	32	32	3.191	0.930
Cumulative Mean						3.035	

Source: Field work (2024)

Decision/threshold mean =2.500

In the table above, it was evident showed that FUE, Zaria have the required facilities for the use of laboratory method towards the practical acquisition of knowledge in computer science for UDUS B.Ed students. This is as their cumulative mean agreement level of 3.035 is greater than the 2.500 decision/threshold mean. Specifically, most of the respondents believed that adequate manpower with requisite knowledge of computers and method can be found in the study area. This view attracted the highest mean agreement level of 3.279 as details showed that while a combined total of 305 were in agreement only 56 were in disagreement. They also asserted that laboratory method is mostly used by experienced lecturers at the expense of their inexperience counterparts. This viewpoint attracted the second

(Assessment of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Practical ... Eva. O. O. & Omoniwa, F. A. 2025)

highest mean agreement level of 3.191 as details showed that while a combined total of 297 were in agreement the rest of 64 respondents were in disagreement.

Research Question Three: What are the effects of laboratory strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS? The respondents questionnaire was adopted alongside Likert four point rating scale of strongly agreed (SA), agreed (A), disagreed (D) and strongly disagreed (SD) respectively. There are five (5) item statements in the table below which the respondents had responded to.

Table 3: Respondents’ opinion on the effects of laboratory strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS

S/N	Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	STD
1.	Exposes the students to what they need to know in computers and how to manipulate it for diverse use.	161	73	90	37	2.091	1.052
2.	Allows for group participation in the class activities which perhaps may take place in the school laboratory.	163	133	33	32	3.182	0.930
3.	Knowledge sharing among the students is difficult where laboratory method is used.	141	112	64	44	2.969	1.028
4.	Interest of slow and un-serious learners are of less concern when laboratory method is put to use.	182	124	35	20	3.296	0.858
5.	The use of laboratory method is incapacitated by poorly trained personnel, lack of adequate materials and say, poor electricity supply in school.	105	94	107	55	2.689	1.050
Cumulative Mean						2.845	

Source: Field work (2024)

Decision/threshold mean =2.500

Table 3 above showed that the effects of the use of laboratory method on the practical acquisition of knowledge in computer science among UDUS B.Ed students in FUE, Zaria is relatively positive and high. This was because the cumulative mean of 2.845 is above the 2.500 decision/threshold mean. Specifically, most of the respondents believed that this method allows for group participation in class activities which perhaps may take place in the school laboratory. This view attracted the highest mean agreement level of 3.182 as details showed that while 296 were in agreement the rest 65 were in disagreement. In the same vein, interest of slow and un-serious learners are of less concern when laboratory method is put to use. The corresponding mean was 3.296 with details showing that while 55 were in agreement the rest 306 were in disagreement.

Summary of the Findings

(Assessment of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Practical ... Eva. O. O. & Omoniwa, F. A. 2025)

The study revealed the following as its findings from the analysis carried out:

1. That the use of laboratory strategy assists in practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students of UDUS to a great extent.
2. UDUS affiliated college in Zaria have the required instructional facilities for the use of laboratory strategy in the practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students. This was in terms of manpower, support facilities like computers and its accessories among others.
3. The effects of use of laboratory strategy in the practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate UDUS students, is relatively positive and high.

Discussion of Findings

Three (3) research questions were formulated and tested in this study titled assessment of laboratory instructional strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS Affiliated Programme. In research question one, extent to which the use of laboratory strategy has assisted undergraduate students in practical skills acquisition in computer science in UDUS was tested. Respondents unanimously agreed that the use of this strategy has helped undergraduate students to acquire practical skills in computer science. This was evident in the aspect of retention of knowledge, attraction of students' interest and in the knowledge of what is computer as well as its workings. The position of Lazarowitz and Tamir cited by Hamidu, Ibrahim and Mohammed, (2014) concur with the findings of this study. This was carefully captured in the distinction between laboratory and traditional classroom learning. They believed that this strategy is student - centered, with students actively engaged in hands-on, minds - on activities using laboratory techniques.

The availability of required instructional facilities for use of laboratory strategy in practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students was tested in research question two. The outcome of this analysis revealed that required instructional facilities are available for use of laboratory strategy in the acquisition of practical skills in computer science among the students. To this end, respondents believed that adequate manpower, computers and its accessories as well as constant electricity are available whenever this instructional strategy is to be used.

(Assessment of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Practical ... Eva. O. O. & Omoniwa, F. A. 2025)

Research question three tested the effects of laboratory strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS. The effect of use of laboratory strategy is noticeable in the practical skills acquisition among the undergraduate students of UDUS in computer science. This was reflected in the responses of respondents that the use of laboratory strategy has effects on exposing the students to what they should know and how to manipulate the computers. It also has the effect of promoting group participation and knowledge sharing amongst the UDUS students. Tobin quoted by Hamidu, Ibrahim and Mohammed (2014) as saying that “laboratory activities appears as a way to learn with understanding and, at the same time, engage in a process of constructing knowledge by doing science.

Recommendations

The following recommendations have been put forward in this study:

1. The need by education managers to advocate for the use of this method by teachers in science related subjects have become essential. Where possible too, they collaborate with policy makers to ensure adequate legislation and strong use of this method in schools to help learners acquire practical knowledge where necessary.
2. This method is student - centeredness and should therefore be encouraged in all teacher training institutions when teaching computer science students. More so, it is more suitable than any other methods in the acquisition of practical knowledge which computer is known for.
3. There is need to carefully monitor the teaching of computer practical by making available all the packages that are necessary with the correct operating system.

Conclusion

The success of the teaching of any school subject lies in the teaching strategy so adopted and how well it is put to use viz-a-viz its purpose. It is therefore imperative to note that there are many instructional strategies, laboratory is thus one of them. Laboratory can thus be considered as one of the most useful teaching strategy in schools that can be applied in computer science as a subject as well as in other science subjects. Vividly, the use of laboratory strategy has positive effects on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students of UDUS. This strategy when used effectively will boost the nation’s economy and help

(Assessment of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Practical ... Eva. O. O. & Omoniwa, F. A. 2025)

reduce the rate of unemployment in the society by producing graduates or graduates to - be who will be self-reliance.

References

- Akuto, G. W., Adoluju, M. O. & Odeh. R. C. (2012). *General Teaching Methods and Strategies in Education*. Abuja: Cubanet Publishers, Nigeria Ltd.
- Chibabi, A. A., Umoru, S. E., Onah, D. O. & Itodo, E. E. (2018). Effect of Laboratory Method on Students' Achievement and Retention in Senior Secondary Schools Biology in Kogi East Senatorial Zone. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)*, Volume 8, Issue 6 Ver. I. (Nov. – Dec. 2018), PP 31 - 39.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approaches*. Sage Publications.
- Hamidu, M. Y., Ibrahim, A. I. & Mohammed, A. (2014). The Use of Laboratory Method in Teaching Secondary School Students: A key to Improving the Quality of Education. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, Volume 5, Issue 9, September, 2014
- Kofo, A. A. (2012). Laboratories and Sustainable Teaching and Learning about Senior Secondary School (SSS) Geography in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, Vol. 2 (4).
- Omoniwa, F. A. (nd). Lecture note on Secondary School Computer Science Laboratory.
- Lazarowitz, R. & Tamir, P. (1994). *Research on using laboratory instruction in science*, In D. L. Gabel. (Ed.) *Handbook of research on science teaching and learning* (pp. 94-130), New York: Macmillan.
- Yin, R. K. (2014). *Case study research: Design and methods*. Sage Publications.